

A Randomized Control Trial of Three Intravenous Dexmedetomidine Doses for Procedural Sedation in Patients Undergoing Minor Gynecological Surgery

Shivcharan Meena¹, Raghvendra Singh²

¹Senior Specialist Obs & Gyne, Govt Medical Center & attached Bangur Hospital, Pali, Rajasthan

²Assistant Professor, Anaesthesiology Govt Medical Center & attached Bangur Hospital, Pali, Rajasthan

Received: 15-04-2022 / Revised: 20-05-2022 / Accepted: 05-06-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Shivcharan Meena

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Minor surgery, despite its short duration, is associated with significant pain and discomfort. Several anaesthetic techniques and pharmacological agents have been used to reduce patient discomfort and facilitate surgical performance. However, procedural sedation and analgesia (PSA) is still preferred over general anaesthesia during short gynaecological procedures. Most analgesics/sedative drugs, such as midazolam, propofol, and fentanyl, which are commonly used for PSA, can potentially prolong sedation and cause respiratory depression and adverse hemodynamic effects, which may result in increased morbidity and unplanned hospitalization as most cases are done as day-care surgery. Dexmedetomidine, a known sedative and analgesic sparing drug that acts on α_2 adrenoceptor, reduces heart rate, blood pressure, and anaesthetic drug requirements in response to any stress. Dexmedetomidine is extensively used as a sedative and analgesic agent in various surgeries, but the optimum dose of dexmedetomidine in these procedures is still unknown.

Aim: The study aims to analyze a randomized control trial of three intravenous dexmedetomidine doses for procedural sedation in patients undergoing minor gynecological surgery.

Method: The study was a randomized control trial conducted at Govt Medical Center & attached Bangur Hospital, Pali, Rajasthan, during the period March 2019 to December 2021. The study population consisted of ASA grade I and II patients aged 18-45 years who were scheduled to undergo short gynecological surgery (20-40 min) under intravenous sedation and analgesia. The study included hysteroscopic copper T removal, dilatation and curettage, hysteroscopic biopsy, and Bartholin cyst excision in the short gynecological surgery. The data was compiled, tabulated, and statistically analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 17 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). Analysis of variance was used for the analysis of mean difference among groups and Chi-square test for grading of sedation, recovery, and discharge.

Result: all patients had a Ramsay Sedation Score of 3 or more. In half of the patients in group A and in one-fourth of the patients in group B, ketamine was required as a rescue drug. None of the patients in group C required any drug supplementation. Moreover, the Modified Aldrete Score (≥ 8) was 21.14 ± 9.99 min and was almost doubled in groups B (39.68 ± 18.39 min) and C (45.38 ± 29.90 min). This difference was statistically significant in the A versus B group and the A versus C group ($p = 0.000$). However, it was comparable between groups

B and C ($p > 0.05$). Patients in group A achieved PADSS score (≥ 9) earlier (148.64 ± 23.56 min) than in group B (177.10 ± 16.16 min) and group C (200.25 ± 18.47 min).

Conclusion: Dexmedetomidine at a dose of $0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{hr}$ provides efficient sedation and analgesia but is associated with significant hemodynamic compromise, whereas dexmedetomidine at a dose of $0.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{hr}$ requires ketamine supplementation at $0.3 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$ to achieve adequate analgesia and sedation without hemodynamic complications

Keywords: anaesthetic techniques, sedative drugs, procedural sedation and analgesia

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Background

Minor surgery, despite its short duration, is associated with significant pain and discomfort [1]. Several anaesthetic techniques and pharmacological agents have been used to reduce patient discomfort and facilitate surgical performance [2]. However, procedural sedation and analgesia (PSA) is still preferred over general anaesthesia during short gynaecological procedures. One of the most important goals of clinicians is patient comfort [3]. When patients present to the emergency department (ED), treating the pain and anxiety that accompany the chief complaint are critical to patient satisfaction and quality of care [4]. Nonetheless, clinicians may underuse sedation, usually from a lack of experience or from unchallenged myths regarding its use [5,6].

Most analgesics/sedative drugs, such as midazolam, propofol, and fentanyl, which are commonly used for PSA, can potentially prolong sedation and cause respiratory depression and adverse hemodynamic effects, which may result in increased morbidity and unplanned hospitalization as most cases are done as day-care surgery [7]. Dexmedetomidine, a known sedative and analgesic sparing drug that acts on α_2 adrenoceptor, reduces heart rate, blood pressure, and anaesthetic drug requirements in response to any stress [8]. Unlike other anaesthetics, it also has a sedative response, mimicking natural sleep without significant respiratory depression [9,10] Minor gynecological procedures

are usually done in outpatient settings. Early discharge with minimal hemodynamic compromise is an essential requirement of these procedures. Many sedative drugs are being used for outpatient surgeries. Of the sedative agents available, dexmedetomidine, which has sedative and analgesic sparing effects, has the best safety profile in the cardiorespiratory system [11]. Therefore, we evaluated the optimum dexmedetomidine dose for providing better procedural sedation.

Dexmedetomidine is extensively used as a sedative and analgesic agent in various surgeries, but the optimum dose of dexmedetomidine in these procedures is still unknown [12]. Thus, the study will evaluate the optimum dexmedetomidine dose for short gynaecological surgery. Moreover, the study will observe perioperative hemodynamic changes and any additional intraoperative adjuvant drug requirements, as well as to evaluate postoperative parameters using the Modified Aldrete Score.

Aim

The study aims to analyze a randomized control trial of three intravenous dexmedetomidine doses for procedural sedation in patients undergoing minor gynecological surgery.

Method and material

The study was a randomized control trial conducted at Govt Medical Center & attached Bangur Hospital, Pali, Rajasthan,

during the period March 2019 to December 2021. The study population consisted of ASA grade I and II patients aged 18-45 years who were scheduled to undergo short gynecological surgery (20-40 min) under intravenous sedation and analgesia. The study included hysteroscopic copper T removal, dilatation and curettage, hysteroscopic biopsy, and Bartholin cyst excision in the short gynecological surgery. The study excluded patients with hypertension, cardiopulmonary diseases, hepatic disease, or who were allergic to any drug from the study. Assuming a 30 min difference in sedative effect between the two groups based on the pilot study with $\alpha = 0.05$ and an 80% power, the minimum number of cases required under each group was 40, making it a total of 120 patients in three group.

The different doses of dexmedetomidine infusion were prepared by medical personnel not involved in the study. We prepared infusion drugs in a 50-ml syringe, and concentration varied in other groups.

In groups A, B, and C, 100 μg , 200 μg , and 300 μg of dexmedetomidine were added in a 50-ml syringe, respectively. Moreover, Heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean blood pressure, peripheral oxygen saturation, and respiratory rate were monitored at the baseline, every 5 min thereafter until surgery was completed, and every 15 min for the first hour followed by every 30 min until the patient was discharged.

Statistical analysis

The data was compiled, tabulated, and statistically analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 17 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). Analysis of variance was used for the analysis of mean difference among groups and Chi-square test for grading of sedation, recovery, and discharge. Results were presented as mean \pm SD. Probability values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Table 1: Age and weight

	Group A (N=40)	Group B (N=40)	Group C (N=40)	P value		
				A vs B	A vs C	B vs C
Age (years)	35.78 \pm 7.54	35.50 \pm 7.39	35.28 \pm 7.14	0.435	0.381	0.445
Weight (kg)	57.78 \pm 7.97	57.00 \pm 6.51	56.8 \pm 6.68	0.318	0.278	0.448

The table has provided the information related to the age and weight and all variables has shown no significant association as p value is higher than 0.05.

Table 2: Sedation score

Parameters	Group A		Group B		Group C	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Sedation score						
3	17	42.5	18	45	13	32.50
4	23	57.5	22	55	27	67.50
Ketamine supplementation	18	45	9	22.5	0	0

According to analysis of table 2 all patients had a Ramsay Sedation Score of 3 or more. In half of the patients in group A and in one-fourth of the patients in group B, ketamine was required as a rescue drug. None of the patients in group C required any drug supplementation

Table 3: Time

	Group A	Group B	Group C	P value		
				A vs B	A vs C	B vs C
Time to achieve Modified Aldrete Score	21.14 ± 9.99	39.68 ± 18.39	45.38 ± 29.90	0.000*	0.000*	0.177
Time to achieve PADSS Score	148.64 ± 23.56	177.10 ± 16.16	200.25 ± 18.47	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*

As per the table 3 in group A, the time taken to achieve the Modified Aldrete Score (≥ 8) was 21.14 ± 9.99 min and was almost doubled in groups B (39.68 ± 18.39 min) and C (45.38 ± 29.90 min). This difference was statistically significant in the A versus B group and the A versus C group ($p = 0.000$). However, it was comparable between groups B and C ($p > 0.05$). Patients in group A achieved PADSS score (≥ 9) earlier (148.64 ± 23.56 min) than in group B (177.10 ± 16.16 min) and group C (200.25 ± 18.47 min). This time, the difference in the achievement of the PADSS score was statistically significant among all three groups ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Procedural sedation and analgesia (PSA) is still preferred over general anaesthesia during short gynaecological procedures. Dexmedetomidine, a known sedative and analgesic sparing drug that acts on α_2 adrenoceptor, reduces heart rate, blood pressure, and anaesthetic drug requirements in response to any stress. Unlike other anaesthetics, it also has a sedative response, mimicking natural sleep without significant respiratory depression. Dexmedetomidine is extensively used as a sedative and analgesic agent in various surgeries, but the optimum dose of dexmedetomidine in these procedures is still unknown. The use of general anaesthesia or central neuraxial blocks during short gynecological procedures is inappropriate. These techniques not only delay the discharge but also increase morbidity. PSA, which combines the use of local anesthesia with intravenous

sedation, can be the technique of choice during such short procedures.

As per the outcome of the study, all patients had a Ramsay Sedation Score of 3 or more. In half of the patients in group A and in one-fourth of the patients in group B, ketamine was required as a rescue drug. None of the patients in group C required any drug supplementation. Moreover, Modified Aldrete Score (≥ 8) was 21.14 ± 9.99 min and was almost doubled in groups B (39.68 ± 18.39 min) and C (45.38 ± 29.90 min). This difference was statistically significant in the A versus B group and the A versus C group ($p = 0.000$). However, it was comparable between groups B and C ($p > 0.05$). Patients in group A achieved PADSS score (≥ 9) earlier (148.64 ± 23.56 min) than in group B (177.10 ± 16.16 min) and group C (200.25 ± 18.47 min). This time, the difference in the achievement of the PADSS score was statistically significant among all three groups ($p < 0.001$). As per the study of Sharma et al., (2022) [13] the time taken to achieve a Modified Aldrete Score ≥ 8 and a Postanesthetic Discharge Scoring system (PADSS) > 9 dose-dependently increased and reached its maximum with higher doses of dexmedetomidine infusion. A similar recovery time was observed in other studies [14]. However, recovery time similar to group C was observed with a dose of $0.2 \mu\text{g/kg/hr}$ in a study. This may be due to the fact that their recovery criteria were different, and the procedure was less painful [15,16].

Conclusion

This study was a prospective, randomized, double-blinded control trial conducted in patients undergoing minor gynecological surgeries to determine the optimum dose of dexmedetomidine infusion for procedural sedation in such surgeries. Moreover, Dexmedetomidine at a dose of 0.6 µg/kg/hr provides efficient sedation and analgesia but is associated with significant hemodynamic compromise, whereas dexmedetomidine at a dose of 0.4 µg/kg/hr requires ketamine supplementation at 0.3 mg/kg to achieve adequate analgesia and sedation without hemodynamic complications.

References

1. Poonai N, Coriolano K, Klassen T, Heath A, Yaskina M, Beer D, Sawyer S, Bhatt M, Kam A, Doan Q, Sabhaney V. Adaptive randomised controlled non-inferiority multicentre trial (the Ketodex Trial) on intranasal dexmedetomidine plus ketamine for procedural sedation in children: study protocol. *BMJ open*. 2020 Dec 1;10(12):e041319.
2. Bajwa SJ. Dexmedetomidine and Ketamine–Comrades on an eternal journey! *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2021 Mar;65(Suppl 1):S1.
3. Farrukh R, Awan WS, Khan AH, Rana AR, Jilani AA, Mahmood K. Comparison of dexmedetomidine and propofol for hemodynamic and recovery characteristics in dilatation and curettage. *The Professional Medical Journal*. 2020 Jun 10;27(06):1244-8.
4. Kaur G, Kaur P, Gupta R, Kullar K, Bhangu GS, Sandhu SS. Discharge readiness after minor gynaecological surgeries comparing dexmedetomidine and ketamine premedication in bispectral index (BIS) guided propofol-based anaesthesia. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2021 Mar;65(Suppl 1):S34.
5. Rekatsina M, Theodosopoulou P, Staikou C. Effects of Intravenous Dexmedetomidine Versus Lidocaine on Postoperative Pain, Analgesic Consumption and Functional Recovery After Abdominal Gynecological Surgery: A Randomized Placebo-controlled Double Blind Study. *Pain Physician*. 2021 Nov 1;24(7):E997-1006.
6. Ma H, Wachtendorf LJ, Santer P, Schaefer MS, Friedrich S, Nabel S, Ramachandran SK, Shen C, Sundar E, Eikermann M. The effect of intraoperative dexmedetomidine administration on length of stay in the post-anesthesia care unit in ambulatory surgery: a hospital registry study. *Journal of Clinical Anesthesia*. 2021 Sep 1; 72:110284.
7. Menshawi MA, Fahim HM. Midazolam–ketamine versus dexmedetomidine–ketamine combinations for anesthesia of pediatric patients undergoing cardiac catheterization. *Ain-Shams Journal of Anesthesiology*. 2019 Dec;11(1):1-7.
8. Lee J, Hwang HW, Jeong JY, Kim YM, Park C, Kim JY. The Effect of Low-Dose Dexmedetomidine on Pain and Inflammation in Patients Undergoing Laparoscopic Hysterectomy. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2022 May 16;11(10):2802.
9. Weerink MA, Barends CR, Muskiet ER, Reyntjens KM, Knotnerus FH, Oostra M, van Bocxlaer JF, Struys MM, Colin PJ. Pharmacodynamic interaction of remifentanyl and dexmedetomidine on depth of sedation and tolerance of laryngoscopy. *Anesthesiology*. 2019 Nov;131(5):1004-17.
10. Masoumi K, Maleki SJ, Forouzan A, Delirrooyfard A, Hesam S. Dexmedetomidine versus midazolam-fentanyl in procedural analgesia sedation for reduction of anterior shoulder dislocation: a randomized clinical trial. *Reviews on recent clinical trials*. 2019 Dec 1;14(4):269-74.
11. Kumari A, Singh AP, Vidhan J, Gupta R, Dhawan J, Kaur J. The sedative and

- propofol-sparing effect of dexmedetomidine and midazolam as premedicants in minor gynecological day care surgeries: A randomized placebo-controlled study. *Anesthesia, Essays and Researches*. 2018 Apr;12(2):423.
12. Sruthi S, Mandal B, Rohit MK, Puri GD. Dexmedetomidine versus ketofol sedation for outpatient diagnostic transesophageal echocardiography: A randomized controlled study. *Annals of cardiac anaesthesia*. 2018 Apr;21(2):143.
 13. Sharma N, Pandey M, Gupta A, Kumar A. A Randomized Control Trial of Three Intravenous Dexmedetomidine Doses for Procedural Sedation in Patients Undergoing Minor Gynaecological Surgery. *Cureus*. 2022 Mar 19;14(3).
 14. Preskorn SH, Zeller S, Citrome L, Finman J, Goldberg JF, Fava M, Kakar R, De Vivo M, Yocca FD, Risinger R. Effect of sublingual dexmedetomidine vs placebo on acute agitation associated with bipolar disorder: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2022 Feb 22;327(8):727-36.
 15. Rekatsina M, Theodosopoulou P, Staikou C. Perioperative Dexmedetomidine or Lidocaine Infusion for the Prevention of Chronic Postoperative and Neuropathic Pain After Gynecological Surgery: A Randomized, Placebo-Controlled, Double-Blind Study. *Pain and Therapy*. 2022 Jun;11(2):529-43.
 16. Erazo, E. W. V., Walles, J. G., Bejarano, H. A., Ustariz, R. J. M., Mejía, A. O., Escobar, P. L. J., Cabra, O. P., & Rodriguez, A. C. E. Reconstruction through the Use of the Posterior Peroneum for Coverage of Defects of the Distal Third of the Leg. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 2022;5(4), 1967–1972.